

8-Theory Reveal Quark Confinement

As Acceleration of Fermions

Toward each other

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the framework of the 8-theory and in particular the main equation, (Lorentz manifold inside EL equation) certain indications regarding the nature of fermions and their behavior relative to each other in the same matrix can be gain. The analysis will take the equation of dark matter and analyze the term that is describing the quark propagation. Reader is assumed to be familiar with the theory thesis as it is needed for an analysis of this paper.

Introduction

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

We already proved that δg can be analyzed as fermions. Suppose we did what we did back in the day, and break it to a sequence of N distinct elements, such;

$$\delta g \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N \in \mathbb{R}, N \rightarrow \infty \quad (3)$$

How would such a set of elements would behave? To answer such a question we can analyze the second term:

$$-\delta g' \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N -\delta g'_i = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\delta g \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = \delta g_i + \delta g_{i+1} + \dots = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$-\delta g' \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N -\delta g'_i = -\delta g'_i + (-\delta g'_{i+1}) + \dots = 0 \quad (6)$$

On one hand the entire series need to vanish, we have a sequence of opposite signs of even numbers, those arbitrary variations derivative describe a acceleration outward, they will try to aspire to reach distance from each other, that is with agreement with the so-called "anti commutation" relation of fermions. Since half of those elements in the set **already have a negative sign** as we proved before:

$$(-\delta g'_{i+1}) \rightarrow -(-\delta g'_{i+1}) \rightarrow +\delta g'_{i+1} \quad (7)$$

Therefore, despite the minus sign, and the outward distancing from each, in accordance to the anti- commutation relation, there is a shift and the minus now varied to a plus:

$$-\delta g' \rightarrow \sum_{i=1}^N -\delta g'_i = -\delta g'_i + (-\delta g'_{i+1}) + \dots = -\delta g'_i + \delta g'_{i+1} \dots = 0 \quad (8)$$

Therefore, that is in agreement with quantum field theory, and their treatment of fermions. They will accelerate toward each other, which can explain the phenomena of quark confinement. The equations show that arbitrary variations of distinct sign will accelerate toward each other, if the reasoning and the mathematical development one presented here is correct.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)